

Blockchains = less government, more market

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Abstract: In this paper we provide a brief survey of the potential of blockchain technology to propel a process of private entrepreneurial discovery of institutions that challenge state hegemony. Entrepreneurs now have access to new tools to develop decentralised private governance across areas which have traditionally been the domain of government action. This may see a radical reshaping of the boundaries of “public” versus “private”. Blockchain may result in less government, and more market based interactions. We introduce institutional cryptoeconomics, and blockchain as a technology which increases the opportunity set of entrepreneurial action. We then survey the potential of blockchain technology to challenge state hegemony in five socioeconomic areas: monetary institutions, the governance of contracting, civil society and social welfare, collective choice and voting, and the verification of identity. We also discuss some challenges and implications of blockchain-based economic infrastructure for public policy and economic regulation. Together these contributions suggest an increasing scope for entrepreneurial action using blockchain that challenges state hegemony, and a necessary shift in the scope of the provision of public goods and government regulatory control.

Keywords: Blockchain, institutions, entrepreneurship, privatisation, role of government

JEL Classifications: O33, O35, O39, P00, P40, P49

1 Introduction

Blockchain is an institutional technology which changes the scope of human interaction which occurs within and across the public and private spheres. While this technology was first used to transact value across the internet without any financial intermediary, it is now being used as part of a process of private entrepreneurial discovery within several areas which have traditionally been the preserve of government. The central finding of the emerging field of institutional cryptoeconomics is that blockchain technology is not just a general-purpose technology, but rather an institutional technology of governance which competes with the other economic institutions of capitalism (see Davidson et al. 2018). Blockchains and the applications built upon them “industrialise trust” (Berg et al. 2017) by mitigating opportunism (à la Williamson, 1985) which enhances the ability for individuals to engage in mutually beneficial – and crucially, voluntary – exchange which was hitherto difficult to transact.

What we mean when we say that blockchain is an institutional technology can be understood by considering what it is and what it does. Blockchain is a distributed ledger technology, that makes use of decentralised consensus algorithms to generate agreement on a “true” public record of socioeconomic facts. This record is kept by each node in a network who support the infrastructure

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(thus it is *distributed*), and each node must agree to the incorporation of a new “block” of records to be entered into the “chain” of such blocks. Thus, it creates protocols concerning what are valid interactions which may be verified as socioeconomic facts entered into a public record. Any such algorithm therefore necessarily creates *institutions* delimiting the scope of interactions deemed by society at large to be valid (North, 1990; Ostrom, 1990; Hodgson, 2010; Lawson, 2016). A multitude of algorithms have been proposed for how such blocks are to be compiled and added by the network to the chain constituting the public record of socioeconomic facts with the common object of achieving *decentralisation* of consensus (Ometoruwa, 2018). Because individuals are free to interact within whatever blockchain-based platforms and associated institutional systems they see fit, and entrepreneurs may develop new systems or “fork” existing ones as they see fit, the technology facilitates a process of institutional *discovery* (Berg and Berg, 2017; Berg, Davidson and Potts, 2018a).

These platforms, and the institutional systems created by the protocols embedded in their infrastructure, are novel because they are of an intermediate form between those we have hitherto observed. Specifically, they share characteristics of the institutional systems underlying both firms and markets as studied by Oliver Williamson (1975; 1985), and yet are not definitively of either kind. They are systems in which voluntary interactions are coordinated within an institutional system to which individuals (in principle) voluntarily agree, and so they share the characteristics of the decentralised, voluntary institutional system which underlies coordination in markets as studied by Friedrich Hayek (1945; 1988). However, the platforms within which those interactions occur, and the institutions embedded within the protocols of their infrastructure are also *designed* in the manner of a business firm’s command-and-control hierarchy as identified by Coase (1937). The platforms and institutional systems which emerge from a blockchain-based infrastructure are thus of an intermediate form which we have hitherto not encountered to any great extent.

In this paper we draw on this field of research to show how, as an institutional technology, blockchain is radically expanding the scope for private enterprise, even to areas which have traditionally been under the hegemony of centralised governmental action. Blockchain is driving a process of institutional entrepreneurial discovery, whereby entrepreneurial action is developing market based solutions to “problems” which have traditionally been the preserve of government. The premise of this paper is simple: to briefly survey areas of socioeconomic interaction which are now more open to market forces and dynamics due to the development of blockchain technology. To do so we examine five main case studies: new monetary institutions (e.g. cryptocurrencies), new forms of smart contracting and dispute resolution, platforms that bolster civil society institutions such as social welfare, new forms of collective choice infrastructure (i.e. a cryptodemocracy), and the decentralised self-sovereign verification of identity. We then offer some comments on the implications of an expansion in private enterprise on how we formulate and conceive public policy.

2 Case studies: where blockchain is expanding the scope for private enterprise

Institutional cryptoeconomics (see the seminal paper by Davidson et al. 2018) shows that blockchain is an institutional technology which allows for the privatised formulation of platforms for socioeconomic interaction in which institutions are emergent from the protocols embedded in that infrastructure. This new form of technology, platform and institutional system presents a challenge to government hegemony in socioeconomic systems at a fundamental level, and expands the scope of private enterprise to the design and formulation of institutions and platforms for socioeconomic interaction. In this section we outline five case studies of how this challenge is

being presently realised in a variety of contexts including money, contracts, civil society, voting and identity.

2.1 Monetary institutions and cryptocurrency

The first, and most spectacular, use of blockchain as an infrastructure for new forms of platforms was of course in the form of cryptocurrency. This expansion of entrepreneurial action into the design and formulation of privatised monetary institutions was of course not unprecedented, but it was given a new vigour by the advent of blockchain consensus algorithms which allow for decentralised consensus across a network where previously centralised governmental authority was relied upon. Blockchain creates an infrastructure for monetary institutions where the record of socioeconomic facts upon which consensus is achieved by a decentralised network is a record of transfers (thus holdings) of purchasing power.

The first such infrastructure was, of course, the famous Bitcoin protocol written by Satoshi Nakamoto (2009). Bitcoin provides a new privatised platform for socioeconomic interaction in which payments may be made in the context of a privatised institutional system concerning the validity of payments. The institutional system created by Bitcoin emerges from the protocols embedded in the blockchain infrastructure upon which it operates. For instance, any transfer of “coins” cannot exceed the total number of “coins” held by the individual, the “coin” must be “signed” by the sender to the exchange, the transfer must be reported to the network at large, there is an option and increasing expectation to “tip” the miners who will compile the block of records and prove it is true by expending “work” and so on. The platform and the institutions which govern it are of the new form hitherto largely unobserved which we have discussed in the sense that Bitcoin provides a platform for voluntary coordination of socioeconomic interaction, yet the protocols from which its institutions emerge were subject to privatised design. It thus increased the scope for private enterprise in monetary institutions, challenging a fundamental hegemony of government action in socioeconomic systems.

Further, blockchain-based cryptocurrencies have expanded the scope for private enterprise and entrepreneurial action in a way that has created new scope for institutional discovery in money. Satoshi Nakamoto’s Bitcoin protocol was followed by the release of a range of new protocols for cryptocurrency platforms with different iterations of the institutions emergent from those protocols. Later iterations of cryptocurrency modified the institutional structure emergent from the protocols embedded within its infrastructure with a view to preserving privacy above all else. For instance, the Monero cryptocurrency requires multiple digital “signatures” be obtained and put to a given “coin” to mask the true origin of payments (van Saberhagen, 2013). Other iterations of cryptocurrency such as Basis (Al-Nadi, Chen and Diao, 2017) modified the institutional structure concerning the creation of new “coins” with a view to using algorithmic central banks to support price stability, giving rise to the “stablecoin” trend. The freedom to crypto-secede or fork from one system and accede to another within cryptocurrency platforms and markets means that such entrepreneurial activity in the design of monetary institutions for blockchain-based cryptocurrencies drives a process of institutional discovery. Thus has blockchain brought about an expansion of the scope of entrepreneurial action in designing privatised monetary institutions (à la Hayek 1976) which drives a process of institutional discovery and challenges a core government hegemony in socioeconomic systems.

2.2 Contractual institutions and the “smart ledger”

Quickly following the use of blockchain to implement cryptocurrency protocols, entrepreneurial action expanded to using blockchain as an infrastructure for the design of privatised institutions

concerning the striking, recording, and executing of contracts. Traditionally subject to the hegemony of government in the form of contract law (Commons, 1924), it was quickly realised that blockchain could be used to achieve consensus on a record of “Smart Contracts”. Blockchain consensus protocols could be used to achieve decentralised consensus on a record of such contracts struck, and keep such a record as could be updated automatically to carry out the provisions of those contracts. It thus created a private institutional system for a privatised platform in which contracts could be struck, recorded, verified and executed, something we have traditionally relied upon a centralised government with coercive authority to do.

One of the first protocols to operationalise Nick Szabo’s (1994) concept of the smart contract was the Ethereum protocol developed by Vitalik Buterin (2013) and Gavin Wood (2014) among others. The blockchain within the Ethereum platform acts as an infrastructure for a system of interaction in which consensus on a “smart ledger” is achieved by a decentralised network. A smart contract is an algorithm which reflects the provisions of a contract, and whose protocols execute automatically upon the realisation of some state of the world. A smart ledger keeps a record of such contracts and executes them when specified conditions are met. The institutions concerning what is a valid smart contract and what is not, and thus the conditions under which a contract may be struck, recorded, and executed emerge from the protocols embedded within the Ethereum protocol. They are of a new form which we have not hitherto seen insofar as the striking of contracts within the protocol is a matter of coordination by voluntary institutions, yet the overall institutional structure emergent from the Ethereum protocols are subject to privatised design. The smart ledger concept of which Ethereum was an early case, made possible by blockchain as an infrastructure, thus expands the scope for private enterprise to the recording, verification and validation of contracts to be executed upon realisation of a particular state of the world – challenging yet another core hegemony of government action.

Of course, being subject to private design, Ethereum was followed by a range of other iterations of smart ledgers with variations on the protocols embedded in their Blockchain infrastructure from which their institutions emerge. Notable examples are the EOS system, which sought to improve on the institutions by which consensus is achieved on the smart ledger by moving from an energy-intensive “proof-of-work” algorithm to a “delegated proof of stake” algorithm, as well as governance issues more generally (Grigg, 2017). NEO seeks to integrate a range of different applications of blockchain technology and deliberately aims to provide a platform for an alternative socioeconomic system formed by smart contracts and decentralised applications built on them. So by expanding the scope for private enterprise and facilitating entrepreneurial action at in the design and formulation of institutions around the striking, recording and executing of contracts which challenges government hegemony, blockchain drives a newly invigorated process of institutional discovery in the core institutions of our society.

2.3 Social welfare systems and the coordination of compassion

As an infrastructure which allows for the recording, storing and validating of data and information by a decentralised and distributed network, blockchain can challenge the hegemony of government action wherever it is necessary to do so for the achieving of objectives. It is entirely conceivable that it could be harnessed to design institutional systems which promote social ends, informed by whatever notion of welfare (for instance Diener et al. 1999; Gropper et al. 2011; Boettke and Subrick 2003; Sen 1999) the designer wishes to promote. This is especially important at the present time where public opinion surveys of trust in traditional organisations which have traditionally had hegemony in the promulgation of social welfare is declining in countries such as the United States, Germany, France, Italy, Canada and Australia, even for non-government organisations (Edelman, 2018). With its combination of automated code, cryptographic security and cryptoeconomic

security, blockchain may be able to challenge this hegemony, and be harnessed to promote social welfare through the design of new platforms with institutions that address problems with privatised systems for promoting social welfare.

It appears that the decline in trust in charities, foundations, social enterprises and other bodies within civil societal space may rest on the potential for opportunism in the presence of asymmetric information between contributors to such projects and the intermediary operators *and* beneficiaries. Unless the institutions which govern such projects create sufficient accountability mechanisms and transparency safeguards in place, it is difficult for the contributor to observe that their financial or in-kind support has flowed through to the beneficiary with minimal disturbance. As highly-publicised financial management and other scandals in certain developed countries have illustrated (Fremont-Smith and Kosaras 2003; Archambeault et al. 2015), there is the not-inconsiderable risk that intermediary groups within the social welfare sector are susceptible to malign or erroneous practices believed to undermine the efficacy and efficiency of organisations, and to compromise the fulfilment of their objectives.

Challenges to the hegemony of government action in social welfare systems by private entities have likely been restricted due to reports of charity and foundation scandals. Even though small numbers of entities have been subject to such scandals, these have likely caused adverse flow-on effects throughout the remainder of the sector, causing potential contributors to withdraw their support from private platforms for promoting social welfare. The reputational impact may have consequences for the capacity of charities and other highly-organised providers within civil society to promote cooperative efficacy (Nair and Sutter 2018). It is here that privatised institutional design for platforms supporting socioeconomic interaction, enabled by blockchain, is likely to bring benefits in terms of reducing possibilities for opportunism. Blockchain-enabled platforms are characterised by institutions which promote:

- Radical transparency: Blockchain allows contributors, beneficiaries, and other interested parties to use blockchain technology to track the verified flow of funds in real time, and to use “smart contract” arrangements to disburse funds to providers on the condition that pre-agreed social impacts have been achieved.
- Reorganisation of assistance models: The use of smart contracts and blockchain code protocols can be combined to create “decentralised collaborative organisations” (DCOs) oriented toward achieving social welfare objectives. These could provide competitive pressure for third-party intermediary programs to ensure desirable social outcomes, and enhance social learning about the effective uses of donor finances and other resources.
- Cost reduction: Blockchain technology could potentially be used to bypass traditional organisational intermediaries not only within the social welfare domain which are susceptible to fraud, hacking and theft, but also financial institutions which impose costs and conditions upon the transfer of finances both domestically and internationally.

In general, entrepreneurial action is now, with the technology, better able to design institutions around the allocation of contributions to realising social welfare objectives and better challenge what has traditionally been the hegemony of government action. Through the process of institutional discovery this feeds, we are likely to be able to better solve the economic problem of designing institutions which allocate resources and distribute funds to vulnerable persons who have nothing to offer in return (Martin and Petersen, 2018).

2.4 Voting and social choice

One of the central realisations of the institutional cryptoeconomics literature is that blockchain is, by its nature, a technology for *governance* (Davidson et al. 2018). It provides an infrastructure for platforms in which institutions may be designed which govern behaviour within that system. In particular, it provides an infrastructure whereby institutions might be designed to coordinate action among a group by aggregating perspectives within that group on how action ought to be coordinated. One of the central coordination problems that governance structures seek to solve is making group decisions. Viewed as an economic problem, collective choice involves both forming and coordinating contextual, distributed and evolving preferences (Hayek, 1945). Institutions for guiding collective action need to be able to coordinate the provision of information which forms those individual perspectives, but also to coordinate those perspectives once they are formed.

The suite of *democratic* institutions available to us is constrained by available technologies. As new technologies are invented—from the kleroterion in Ancient Athens that facilitated sortition (Dow 1939), to the modern printing press that enabled ballot papers—new forms of collective choice infrastructure become available. Technologies help us to create institutions that economise on the costs of making collective choices, including developing new ways to coordinate information to form those preferences. Those costs include those derived from making choices under uncertainty (i.e. decision costs) and the costs of delegating power to representatives (i.e. agency costs) (Allen et al. forthcoming).

Blockchain is a novel technology for democratic governance insofar as it provides scope for private enterprise to design institutions for the formation and aggregation of perspectives on collective action in a manner where validation is obtained by a decentralised and distributed network. It provides a technology whereby votes may be distributed and aggregated on particular questions of collective action promulgated throughout the network according to particular institutions specific to a given blockchain. We can call the ordering of collective choice through blockchain a cryptodemocracy (see Allen et al. 2018; Allen et al. forthcoming). A cryptodemocracy has polycentric characteristics. It is characterised by dispersed centres of decision making that emerge from the actions of voters and political entrepreneurs in response to any range of problems of collective choice from public elections to corporate and union governance. This suggests a more competitive and dynamic discovery process.

This is profound, as the institutions for forming and aggregating preferences have traditionally been the hegemony of centralised authorities which validate the public record of aggregated perspectives, and so the institutional possibilities for coordinating collective action have been restricted. For instance, even within the most advanced liberal democracies, the bundle of rights that citizens hold is highly constrained. Voters are often placed within defined electoral boundaries, vote only every set number of years, and votes generally cannot be bought or sold in a market due to the necessity of the secret ballot. Taking a property rights perspective of voting rights (i.e. Demsetz 1967), the bundle of rights that citizens are afforded is a heavily restricted bundle because existing technologies struggle to economise the costs of allowing for an expanded set of rights.

Because voting rights can be maintained and exercised through a shared decentralised ledger using blockchain, it is an infrastructure which allows for more liquid and emergent coordination of voting rights, including the buying and selling of votes and the delegation and re-delegation of votes through a series of contracts (Allen et al. 2018b; Berg 2017a, 2017b). While contemporary, centralised and government-dominated democracies routinely reduce the rights that voters can express—such as secret ballots preventing voting markets (Brent 2006; Crook and Crook 2007; Heckelman 1995; Kam 2017)—blockchain holds promise to expand the bundle of voting rights that people hold. So we can say that blockchain opens up new institutional possibilities that are

based on emergent spontaneous coordination, polycentric grouping of decision making power, and a more contractarian democratic order (Allen et al.; forthcoming; Allen et al. 2018).

By providing scope for private enterprise in this manner even in the most foundational of institutions in society, blockchain therefore allows for greater institutional discovery in the coordination of social choice and collective action. It facilitates spontaneous voluntary adaptation of institutions for coordinating social choice to changing circumstances and challenges what has been hitherto the province of centralised and particularly government action. Cryptodemocracy might very well make private institutions around forming and aggregating perspectives on social choice comparatively institutionally efficient to public institutions as they come to solve problems of collective action in more effective ways.

2.5 Establishment and verification of identity

Some level of assurance over the attributes of a counterparty to exchange is necessary for all but the least sophisticated transactions (Berg et al. 2017, 2018). The economic and political interactions individuals enter into are (usually) contingent on the presentation of proof as to particular identity attributes. Traditionally, these attributes have been typically proven using government issued identity documents; commercial exchange typically ‘free-rides’ off government issued identities (Berg et al. 2017). Recently, we have also seen less official, but nonetheless important online identities controlled by a small number of commercial entities such as Google, Facebook and Twitter which are used to monetise an individual’s habits, tastes and preferences via online advertising (Der et al., 2017), and over which the corporations have near complete authority over maintaining (transforming them into quasi-political entities). The institutions by which we establish and prove identity has therefore traditionally been to use entries in a centralised ledger.

Blockchain based identity management systems, combined with private storage of digital identity attributes, have the potential to challenge and supplant the traditionally core government hegemony over the institutions by which public identity is established, accessed and managed. Blockchain protocols are currently being developed to allow for the privatised, decentralised and distributed administration and governance of institutions by which identity is established, validated and proved. In general, blockchain based identity infrastructure provides a means to give certainty that an individual owns some identity attribute, while simultaneously obfuscating previous activities of that individual, thereby giving strong privacy protections (Der et al., 2017). Crucially, these Blockchain-based identity platforms allow individuals to prove who they are for the purposes of commercial exchange without entirely relying on the actions or cooperation of any centralised authority such as a government or commercial entity with a monopoly on the means of coercion.

Loffreto (2012), Searls (2012) and Allen (2016) are among those who have developed the concept of self-sovereign identity, which expands the opportunity set of entrepreneurial actions around the institutions of identity and identity management. Self-sovereign identity places the management of identity attributes within the purview of the individual and, among other things, emphasises characteristics of individual control, portability, consent and disclosure minimalisation (see Allen, 2016). In general, it provides individuals the opportunity to have complete and persistent control over their identity attributes, while maintaining the ability to disclose only those attributes they desire to participate in exchange. This is in stark contrast to the ways in which government entities normally provide public identity institutions. Identity provision is normally one of administrative necessity (Searls, 2012), whereby the state seeks maximum legibility (à la Scott, 1998) such that their populations can be embraced (à la Torpey, 2000) for the purposes of taxation, conscription and welfare administration. With self-sovereign identity, the crucial characteristics of control and portability over one’s personal identity information, enabled through decentralised blockchain

platforms and complemented by allied technology such as zero-knowledge proofs, creates the prospect for hitherto impossible institutions to be established by entrepreneurial action for establishing and verifying identity which are controlled by individuals.

For instance, self-sovereign identity platforms such as Sovrin (2018) and Meeco (2018) are currently being developed to allow individuals to share their identity attributes as part of exchange without relying on the continued cooperation of government or commercial entities, while also allowing individuals to reduce the amount of identity information they expose in the first place. This shift presents new institutional opportunities for the governance of individual identity whereby entrepreneurs can develop new applications which allow individuals to manage, and perhaps even monetise, their own identity data. By providing scope for private enterprise so that entrepreneurial action is possible in the design of institutions concerning such a fundamental aspect of life as the establishing, verification and proving of identity, blockchain thus challenges the hegemony of government action and provides greater scope for institutional discovery of more effective ways to manage and verify identity.

3 Public policy implications and conclusion

The policy consequences of the institutional entrepreneurial dynamics we have outlined are potentially far reaching. In the first decade of their existence, the policy response to blockchains has been focused on integrating blockchain applications—cryptocurrencies and initial coin offerings—into taxation and securities law (see Novak 2018; Novak and Pochesneva 2018). But new institutional forms enabled by blockchain technology will present new challenges and opportunities for the implementation of public policy.

One example of such challenges is the rise of the V-form organisation, where the vertical integration of a supply chain is outsourced to a blockchain (Berg, Davidson and Potts 2018b). To the extent that V-form organisations are adopted by industry, they imply smaller, disaggregated firms, networked together with large scale protocols. Smaller firms will undercut the dynamic of labour relations in economies where collective bargaining between large businesses and large unions is prevalent. This has further complex implications for global tax competition, competition policy, and pension funds and other sovereign wealth funds that are limited to investing in the large public companies that have dominated the twentieth century.

Berg, Davidson and Potts (2018c) find that this ‘dehierarchicalisation’—the competitive replacement of hierarchical organisations with decentralised governance—also potentially disrupts a long standing regulatory dynamic which, following Marx, has sought to tame the consequences of the concentration of power in hierarchical firms. In this argument, the growth of the regulatory state (Glaeser and Shleifer 2003) has been a response not only to the costs of opportunism in a complex economy, but also to mitigate the reduction in innovation that regulation has caused. Dehierarchicalisation undercuts this dynamic, allowing for complex economic activity to be governed without the cost of hierarchical organisation. As a consequence, regulatory control which seeks to tame hierarchy is no longer necessary.

We might be tempted to argue, however, that government will always have a role in regulating socioeconomic interaction within particular institutional systems to prevent or arbitrate disputes, including those implemented on blockchain-based platforms. Much public policy and regulation is designed to mitigate the costs of opportunism—that is, boundaries of potential distrust between buyers and sellers, owners and managers. Traditionally, governments have provided the infrastructure to both enforce contracts and adjudicate disputes arising from opportunistic behaviour. We can see however, that the development of new institutions using blockchains that

can complement, or compete with, the existing suite of economic institutions for regulating opportunistic behaviour even here changes the appropriate balance between regulatory control and market control (Berg et al. forthcoming).

While a number of scholars argue that the existing legal frameworks will continue to provide arbitration in a blockchain context, new, algorithmic arbitration systems and distributed jurisdictions are being developed to provide a competing service (De Filippi and Wright 2018). Blockchain offers private enterprise a new mechanism to manage and regulate opportunistic behaviour. For example, smart contracts are self-enforcing. In their ‘pure’ form—that is, where all triggers and conditions of the contract are managed on-chain—they do not need any external authority to enforce or otherwise manage disputes. Of course, this is only true on the margin. Smart contracts that interface with the real, non-blockchain world—that require external triggers or involve incomplete contracts—need dispute resolution (arbitration) mechanisms. Some of those arbitration mechanisms may be provided through decentralised blockchain-based infrastructure acting as ‘oracles’ into smart contracts (Allen et al. 2018b).

Further, Cowen and Tabarrok (2015) have argued that technologies that allow buyers to rate sellers (such as Uber and eBay) reduce asymmetric information which creates the market for lemons (Akerlof 1970). The lemons problem is a problem of trust – that buyers have less access to information about the goods that are on sale than the sellers. Blockchains provide further protection against opportunism in this context by providing a secure and validated record of such ratings as Cowen and Tabarrok have argued reduces the problem of asymmetric. For instance, distributed ledgers can reliably link to reviews to pseudonymous identities and prevent platforms from altering reviews after the fact. At the margin this implies still less need for regulation and the legal system to mitigate against opportunistic behaviour in the market.

Institutions improve when they are subject to discovery processes by a variety of actors. In this paper we draw on institutional cryptoeconomics to show how, as an institutional technology, blockchain is radically expanding the scope for private enterprise and driving a process of institutional discovery. Insofar as blockchain is allowing for more experimentation with the design of even institutions which have traditionally been the province of government action, it offers significant opportunities for the improvement of the institutions which organise our society and interactions within it. These challenges are being posed to areas of socioeconomic action which have traditionally been core functions of the government. This is enabled by the nature of blockchain technology, which provides infrastructure for platforms within which designed institutions may be implemented in the protocols embedded within the platform governing what is and isn’t a valid interaction to be entered into the public record.

References

- Akerlof, G. A. (1970). “The Market for ‘Lemons’: Quality Uncertainty and the Market Mechanism”, *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 84(3), pp.488-500
- Allen, Christopher, (2016) “The Path to Self-Sovereign Identity”, available at URL: <http://www.lifewithalacrity.com/2016/04/the-path-to-self-sovereign-identity.html> (accessed 20/11/2018)
- Allen, Darcy W.E. (2017), “The Private Governance of Entrepreneurship: An Institutional Approach to Entrepreneurial Discovery”, Doctoral Thesis, RMIT School of Economics, Finance and Marketing, Melbourne, Australia.
- Allen, Darcy W.E. (forthcoming), “Entrepreneurial Exit: Developing the Cryptoeconomy”, in Swan, M, Potts, J, Takagi, S, Tasco, P, Witte, F (eds.), *Blockchain Economics*, World Scientific.

- Allen, Darcy W.E., Lane, Aaron M., and Poblet, Marta, (2018b) “The Governance of Blockchain Dispute Resolution”, Conference paper presented to The Australasian Law and Economics Conference. Brisbane, Australia 2018.
- Allen, Darcy W.E., Berg, Chris and Lane, AM. (forthcoming), *Cryptodemocracy*, World Scientific
- Allen, Darcy W.E., Berg, C, Lane, AM and Potts, J (2018), “Cryptodemocracy and its institutional possibilities”, *The Review of Austrian Economics*, pp.1-12
- Archambeault, Deborah S., Webber, Sarah and Greenlee, Janet, (2015) “Fraud and Corruption in U.S. Nonprofit Entities: A Summary of Press Reports 2008-2011”, *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 44(6), pp.1194-1224.
- Berg, Alastair and Berg, Chris, (2017) “Exit, Voice, and Forking”, available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3081291>
- Berg, Alastair, Berg, Chris, Davidson, Sinclair and Potts, Jason, (2017) “The Institutional Economics of Identity”, available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3072823>
- Berg, Alastair, Berg, Chris, Davidson, Sinclair and Potts, Jason, (2018) “Identity as Input to Exchange”, available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3171960>
- Berg, Chris, (2017a), “Delegation and Unbundling in a Crypto-Democracy”, RMIT University Working Paper
- Berg, Chris, Davidson, Sinclair and Potts, Jason, (2017) “Blockchains industrialise trust”, available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3074070>
- Berg, Chris, (2017b), “Populism and Democracy: A Transaction Cost Diagnosis and a Cryptodemocracy Treatment”, available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3071930>
- Berg, Chris, Davidson, Sinclair and Potts, Jason, (2018a) “Institutional Discovery and Competition in the Evolution of Blockchain Technology”, available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3220072>
- Berg, Chris, Davidson, Sinclair and Potts, Jason, (2018b) “Outsourcing vertical integration: introducing the V-form network”, Medium, 27 March, available at <https://medium.com/cryptoeconomics-australia/outourcing-vertical-integration-introducing-the-v-form-network-78e1aa93a814>
- Berg, Chris, Davidson, Sinclair and Potts, Jason, (2018c) “Capitalism after Satoshi: Blockchains, dehierarchisation, innovation policy and the regulatory state”, available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3299734>
- Berg, Chris, Davidson, Sinclair and Potts, Jason, (forthcoming) *How to understand the blockchain economy: an introduction to institutional cryptoeconomics*, Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Boettke, Peter and Subrick, J. Robert, (2003) “Rule of Law, Development, and Human Capabilities”, *Supreme Court Law Review*, 10, pp.109-126.
- Buterin, Vitalik (2013) “Ethereum: A Next-Generation Smart Contract and Decentralized Application Platform”, available at URL: <http://ethereum.org/ethereum.html> (17/09/2018)
- Coase, Ronald, (1937) “The Nature of the Firm”, *Economica*, 4(16), pp.386-405
- Commons, John R., (1924) *Legal Foundations of Capitalism*, MacMillan & Co., New York
- Cowen, Tyler and Tabarrok, Alex (2015) “The End of Asymmetric Information”, *Cato Unbound*, available at URL: <https://www.cato-unbound.org/2015/04/06/alex-tabarrok-tyler-cowen/end-asymmetric-information>
- Crook, Malcom and Crook, Tom, (2007), “The advent of the secret ballot in Britain and France, 1789–1914: From public assembly to private compartment”, *History*, 92(308), pp. 449-71
- Davidson, Sinclair and De Filippi, Primavera and Potts, Jason, (2018) “Blockchains and the economic institutions of capitalism”, *Journal of Institutional Economics*, 14(4), pp.639-658
- De Filippi, Primavera and Wright, Aaron, (2018) *Blockchain and the Law*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts
- Der, Uwe, Jähnichen, Stefan and Sürmeli, Jan, (2017) “Self-sovereign Identity – Opportunities and Challenges for the Digital Revolution”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1712.01767, available at URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.01767.pdf> (accessed 20/11/2018)

- Demsetz, Harold, (1967), "Toward a theory of property rights", *American Economic Review*, 57(2), pp. 347-59
- Diener, Ed, Suh, Eunkook, Lucas, Richard E. and Smith, Heidi, (1999) "Subjective Well-Being: Three Decades of Progress", *Psychological Bulletin*, 125(2), pp.276-302
- Dow, Sterling (1939), "Aristotle, the Kleroteria, and the Courts", *Harvard Studies in Classical Philology*, 50, pp.1-34
- Edelman (2018) "2018 Edelman Trust Barometer: Global Report", available at URL: https://www.edelman.com/sites/g/files/aatuss191/files/2018-10/2018_Edelman_Trust_Barometer_Global_Report_FEB.pdf (accessed 16 November 2018)
- Fremont-Smith, Marion. R. and Kosaras, Andras, (2003) "Wrongdoing by officers and directors of charities: A survey of press reports 1995-2002", *Exempt Organization Tax Review* 42, pp.25-59
- Glaeser, Edward L., and Shleifer, Andrei (2003) "The Rise of the Regulatory State." *Journal of Economic Literature* 41(2), pp.401-425.
- Grigg, Ian, (2017) "EOS – an introduction", available at URL: https://eos.io/documents/EOS_An_Introduction.pdf (accessed 17/09/2018)
- Gropper, Daniel M., Lawson, Robert A., and Thorne Jr., Jere T, (2011) "Economic Freedom and Happiness" *Cato Journal*, 31(2) pp.237-255
- Hayek, Friedrich, (1945) "The Use of Knowledge in Society", *American Economic Review*, 25(4), pp.519-530
- Hayek Friedrich, (1976) *Denationalisation of Money: The Argument Refined*, Ludwig von Mises Institute.
- Hayek, Friedrich, (1988) *The Fatal Conceit*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago
- Heckelman, Jac C., (1995), "The effect of the secret ballot on voter turnout rates", *Public Choice*, 82(1-2), pp.107-24
- Hodgson, Geoffrey, Knudsen, Thorbjorn, (2010) *Darwin's Conjecture*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago
- Kam, Christopher (2017), "The secret ballot and the market for votes at 19th-century British elections", *Comparative Political Studies*, 50(5), pp.594-635
- Lawson, Tony, (2016) "Comparing Conceptions of Social Ontology: Emergent Social Entities and/or Institutional Facts?", *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour*, 46(4), pp.359-399
- Loffreto, Devon, (2012) "What is 'Sovereign Source Authority'?", available at URL: <https://www.moxytongue.com/2012/02/what-is-sovereign-source-authority.html> (accessed 20/11/2018)
- Martin, Adam and Petersen, Matias, (2018) "Poverty Alleviation as an Economic Problem", *Cambridge Journal of Economics*, available at URL: <https://doi.org/10.1093/cje/bey010>.
- Meece, (2018) "Zero Knowledge Proofs of the Modern Digital Life", available at URL: <https://digify.com/a/#/view/55d40168f67c4676bed9e49ed99832fc> (accessed 20/11/2018)
- Nakamoto, Satoshi, (2009), "Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System", available at URL: <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf> (accessed 14/09/2018)
- Nair, Malavika and Sutter, Daniel, (2018) "The Blockchain and Increasing Cooperative Efficacy", *The Independent Review* 22(4), pp.529-550.
- Novak, Mikayla, (2018) "Crypto-friendliness: Understanding blockchain public policy", available at SSRN: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3215629
- Novak, Mikayla and Pochesneva, Anastasia, (2018) "Toward a Crypto-Friendly Index for the APEC Region", available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3277266>
- North, Douglass, (1990) *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
- Ometorowa, Toju, (2018) "Solving the Blockchain Trilemma: Decentralization, Security & Scalability", CoinBureau.com, available at URL: <https://www.coinbureau.com/analysis/solving-blockchain-trilemma/> (accessed 17/09/2018)
- Ostrom, Elinor, (1990) *Governing the Commons*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
- Scott, James, (2008) *Seeing Like a State* Yale University Press, New Haven

- Searls, Doc, (2012) “Sovereign-source vs. administrative identity”, ProjectVRM, available at URL: <https://blogs.harvard.edu/vrm/2012/03/25/sovereign-source-vs-administrative-identity/> (accessed 20/11/2018)
- Sen, Amartya, (1999) *Development as Freedom*, Knopf, New York
- Sovrin, (2018) “Sovrin™: A Protocol and Token for Self-Sovereign Identity and Decentralized Trust”, available at URL: <https://sovrin.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Sovrin-Protocol-and-Token-White-Paper.pdf> (accessed 20/11/2018)
- Szabo, Nick, (1994) “Smart Contracts”, available at URL: http://www.fon.hum.uva.nl/rob/Courses/InformationInSpeech/CDROM/Literature/LOT_winterschool2006/szabo.best.vwh.net/smart.contracts.html (accessed, 17/08/2018)
- Torpey, John (2000) *The Invention of the Passport*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
- van Saberhagen, Nicolas (2013) “CryptoNote v 2.0”, available at URL: <https://cryptonote.org/whitepaper.pdf> (accessed 14/11/2018)
- Williamson, Oliver, (1975) *Markets and Hierarchies*, The Free Press, New York
- Williamson, Oliver, (1985) *The Economic Institutions of Capitalism*, Free Press, New York
- Wood, Gavin, (2014) “Ethereum: A Secure Decentralised Generalised Transaction Ledger EIP-150 Revision”, available at URL: <http://yellowpaper.io> (accessed 17/09/2018)